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amino)-thiazoles did not give any reaction product with *p*-substituted phenyl sulphonyl chloride.

2-Aryl amino-4-[4'-(benzene sulphonamido)-phenyl]-thiazoles

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VARIOUS 2-substituted amino-4-[4'(benzene sulphonamido)-phenyl]-thiazoles have been synthesized to study their anti bacterial activity.

The starting materials, 4-(4'-aminophenyl)-2-aryl amino)-thiazoles, were synthesized by condensing *p*-acetamido- ω -chloroacetophenone with substituted phenyl thioureas in alcohol. The thioureas used were phenyl, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chlorophenyl, *o*-methoxyphenyl, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-methylphenyl, *o*-nitrophenyl and (2'-pyridyl)-thioureas. 4-(4'-Acetamidophenyl)-2-(substituted amino)-thiazoles were hydrolysed to 4-(4'-aminophenyl)-2-(substituted amino)-thiazoles (I) which on reacting with *p*-substituted phenyl sulphonyl chloride yielded compounds of the type (II). It should be noted here that 4-(4'-acetamido-phenyl)-2-(substituted

Hence, the primary amino group condenses with sulphonyl chloride group in the formation of the compounds (II). The ir spectra confirmed the presence of O=S=O grouping in these compounds from their strong absorption at $\sim 1350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (asymmetric stretch) and $\sim 1125\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (symmetric stretch). The thiazole nucleus showed absorption bands at 1570-1530, 1438-1380 and 1390-1330 cm^{-1} . The two bands in the region 3500-3260 and 3220-3180 cm^{-1} are due to $-\text{SO}_2-\text{NH}$ and $-\text{NH}-$ stretchings. The $-\text{NH}-$ bending absorption was observed at 1610-1580 cm^{-1} .

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. The ir spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer-137 spectrophotometer in KBr phase.

Synthesis of 4-(4'-aminophenyl)-2-(substituted amino)-thiazoles (I): A mixture of *p*-acetamido- ω -chloro-acetophenone (0.1 mole), substituted phenyl

TABLE-1

Substituents R	4-(4'-aminophenyl)-2(substituted amino)-thiazole (I)		4-[4'-(<i>p</i> -substituted benzene sulphonamido)-phenyl]-2(substituted amino)-thiazoles (II)		Substituent R'			NH ₂				
	m.p. °C	N% Found (Calcd.)	S% Found (Calcd.)	m.p. °C	N% Found (Calcd.)	S% Found (Calcd.)	-CH ₃		m.p. °C	N% Found (Calcd.)	S% Found (Calcd.)	
							-NHCOOCH ₃					
Phenyl	121	15.52 (15.72)	11.54 (11.98)	142	10.12 (9.97)	15.30 (15.20)	152	11.97 (12.07)	14.48 (14.16)	162	13.14 (13.24)	15.60 (15.16)
<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	210	13.84 (13.95)	10.52 (10.63)	196	9.14 (9.28)	14.32 (14.06)	192	11.34 (11.28)	12.62 (12.35)	196	12.92 (12.24)	13.92 (14.08)
<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	104	13.81 (13.95)	10.61 (10.63)	179	9.40 (9.29)	14.40 (14.06)	124	11.27 (11.28)	12.59 (12.85)	191	12.28 (12.24)	14.37 (14.09)
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	212	13.75 (13.95)	10.65 (10.63)	192	9.37 (9.28)	14.29 (14.06)	183	11.37 (11.28)	12.59 (12.85)	189	12.31 (12.24)	14.29 (14.09)
<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	203	14.25 (14.14)	10.53 (10.77)	187	9.50 (9.27)	14.00 (14.19)						
<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	142	14.65 (14.95)	10.32 (11.39)	138	9.71 (9.65)	14.92 (14.71)	192	11.74 (11.68)	13.22 (13.38)	180	12.93 (12.81)	14.62 (14.67)
<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	157	15.01 (14.95)	11.49 (11.39)	217	9.73 (9.65)	14.95 (14.71)	146	11.57 (11.68)	13.29 (13.38)	226	12.87 (12.81)	14.06 (14.67)
<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	146	17.93 (18.12)	10.32 (10.25)	149	11.85 (12.02)	14.71 (13.78)	145	13.81 (13.75)	12.35 (12.75)	298	15.10 (14.95)	13.62 (13.73)
(2'-Pyridyl)-	240	20.74 (20.89)	11.72 (11.94)				179	14.94 (15.09)	14.98 (15.18)	184	16.64 (16.55)	15.29 (15.18)

thiourea (0.1 mole) and ethanol (55 ml) was refluxed for 1.5 hr. 4-(4'-Acetamido-phenyl)-2-(substituted amino)-thiazoles were isolated following the method of Hantzsh¹. These compounds were refluxed with 2 N NaOH (14 ml) and ethanol for 45 min. Ethanol was distilled off and the reaction mixture poured in water. The solid product was filtered, washed and crystallised from ethanol. The melting points and analysis are given in Table 1.

General procedure for the synthesis of 4-[4'-(p-substituted benzene sulphonamido)-phenyl]-2-(substituted amino)-thiazoles (II): A mixture of 4-(4'-amino-phenyl)-2-(substituted amino)-thiazole (0.01 mole), p-substituted benzene sulphonyl chloride (0.01 mole) and dry pyridine (20 ml) was heated on water bath for 1.0 hr and then kept at room temp for 36 hr. The reaction mixture was poured in ice containing little conc H₂SO₄ with constant stirring. The crude product washed with dil NaHCO₃ soln and distilled water, was crystallised from ethanol.

p-Methyl- and p-acetamido benzene sulphonyl chloride were condensed with different 4-(4'-amino-phenyl)-2-(substituted amino)-thiazoles. The 4-(4'-N-acetamido sulphonamido)-2-(substituted amino)-thiazole derivatives were hydrolysed with 2 N NaOH to 4-(4'-sulphanilamido)-2-(substituted amino)-thiazoles and crystallised from ethanol. The melting points and analysis are given in Table 1.

Activity: Some representative compounds from each series were tested against four different organisms viz., *V. comma*, *M. tuberculosis*, *S. typhi* and *S. aureus*. None of them was found to be active.

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Selective Methylation of Quercetin and Myricetin

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SEVERAL methods are known for selective methylation of flavonoids¹⁻³. The key factor permitting methylation of certain hydroxyl groups in preference to others is the differential acidity of the hydroxyl groups placed at different positions of the flavone nucleus. The pioneering work in this

direction was done by Simpson and Beton¹ who studied the methylation of flavones and flavonols with dimethyl sulphate in refluxing acetone in presence of sodium bicarbonate and postulated the acidity order of the flavone hydroxyls as 7 > 4' > 3' > 3 on the basis of the results. But recent spectroscopic data, particularly the observation⁴ that flavones bearing a hydroxyl group at 3 rather than 3' position exhibit bathochromic shift in uv spectra in presence of a weak base like sodium acetate, clearly indicate the enhanced acidity of the hydroxyl group at 3 position compared to that at 3' position. This is clearly reflected in our selective methylation experiments with polyhydroxyflavones like myricetin (1, R=R₁=R₂=H) and quercetin (2, R=R₁=R₂=H) which gave in our hands 3,7,4'-trimethyl ethers (1 and 2, R=R₂=H, R₁=Me) as major products and 3,7,3',4'-tetramethyl ethers (1 and 2, R=H, R₁=R₂=Me) as the minor constituents. It was further observed that replacement of sodium bicarbonate with anhydrous sodium acetate gave essentially 7,4'-dimethyl ethers and the major product of methylation of quercetin with dimethyl sulphate in presence of sodium acetate was 7,4'-dimethylquercetin (3). The partially methylated flavonols were fully characterised from detailed spectral analysis of the compounds, their derivatives and also by degradative studies in some cases. Thus, the major compound obtained from myricetin yielded a triethylether (1, R₁=Me, R=R₂=Et)

which on alkali hydrolysis afforded ω,4-dimethoxy-2-ethoxy-6-hydroxy-acetophenone (4) and 3,5-diethyl-4-methyl gallic acid. Similarly, ethylation and subsequent alkali hydrolysis of the major product obtained from quercetin furnished the acetophenone, 4 and O-ethyl-isovanillic acid.

Experimental

Melting points were taken on a Toshniwal apparatus and are uncorrected. UV spectra were recorded on a Cary-14 instrument using spectrograde methanol (E.M.). IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 720 spectrophotometer in Nujol mull. ¹H NMR spectra were taken on Bruker WH-90 and Varian A-60D instruments using deuteriochloroform as solvent and TMS as internal standard. Anhydrous Na₂SO₄ was normally used